

PERCEPTION ON MODERN HOMOPHOBIA OF DIVERSE GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

The way different generations perceive modern homophobia is largely influenced by their exposure to LGBTQ+ issues and their varying social contexts. Older generations often grew up in environments where prejudice against homosexuals was more prevalent and socially acceptable, which may have contributed to deeply ingrained biases. The purpose of this study is to examine how people across generations view contemporary homophobia in order to gain a better understanding of how perceptions of LGBTQ+ individuals have evolved over time. Evaluating the views of different age cohorts will help uncover generational differences and the underlying factors that shape these perspectives. One of the goals is to explore the factors that influence homophobic beliefs. Other objectives include assessing how the media and educational systems impact these viewpoints, as well as examining the significance of individual experiences and societal shifts. Ultimately, this study aims to provide a thorough understanding of how attitudes toward LGBTQ+ issues are shaped by generational contexts, with implications for promoting inclusivity and tolerance in contemporary society.

Keywords: *Generations, LGBTQ+, Prejudice, Homosexuals, Homophobia*

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Perceptions of modern homophobia vary greatly among generations due to differences in social circumstances and exposure to LGBTQ+ concerns. Older generations often grew up in environments where homophobic sentiments were more socially acceptable and widespread, potentially contributing to more deeply rooted biases. The goal of this study is to investigate how people perceive contemporary homophobia across generations, in order to better understand how attitudes toward LGBTQ+ individuals have evolved and differed over time. The study aims to identify generational disparities and the underlying factors that influence these viewpoints by evaluating the opinions of various age cohorts. The objectives include understanding the historical, cultural, and social factors that shape homophobic attitudes, evaluating the impact of media and education on these perspectives, and investigating the role of personal experiences and societal changes. Finally, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how generational circumstances influence attitudes toward LGBTQ+ issues, with implications for promoting tolerance and inclusivity in modern society.

According to Pinaga (2023), Gloc-9's song "Sirena," which portrays the experiences of LGBT members from childhood to adulthood by presenting an image of how they deal with their sexual preferences and how society establishes its perception of LGBT people, has become incredibly popular and controversial in the Philippines, particularly among the LGBT community, which is the song's primary subject matter. Therefore, in the conservative and traditional Filipino culture, the main factors influencing how LGBT people cope with their sexuality are religious convictions, cultural norms, and expectations from their families.

Modern homophobia hinders social progress by impeding efforts toward achieving equality for all citizens. Discrimination against LGBTQ+ individuals denies them basic human rights, such as marriage equality and protection against hate crimes. It also fosters an environment where homophobic rhetoric is normalized and perpetuated. Homophobia comprises negative attitudes, feelings, or behaviors toward individuals who identify as lesbian or gay (Madžarević and Soto-Sanfiel, 2018).

Homophobia can manifest in various forms, including verbal harassment, physical violence, discrimination, and exclusion from social or institutional settings (Amistad, A. 2022)

According to (Ventriglio et al, 2021), the concept of heteronormativity— which asserts that heterosexuality is the norm for all social and sexual interactions and that homosexuality is an aberrant variation— forms the basis for most homophobic beliefs. Unfortunately, homophobia remains a prevalent and widespread social, political, and religious belief system, even in places where acceptance of sexual diversity and same-sex marriage has increased. This is particularly evident in the mental health criteria concerning individuals who are targets of homophobia.

In the research topic titled *Trans Visibility: A Look into Filipinos' Attitudes Toward Transgender Individuals* (Reyes, 2023), it is noted that compared to other LGBTQ+ members, transgender people have received very little research attention. This is particularly true in the Philippines, where transgender individuals are more frequently featured in the media. The findings show that respondents from public schools were more educated about the policy's requirements. In terms of attitudes, both groups of respondents generally accepted the diversity within the LGBTQ+ community.

Adolescents whose identities include lesbian, gay, bisexual, and sexually questioning (LGBQ) individuals, and who are teased for their sexual orientation, are particularly vulnerable to the negative effects of bullying. Students who do not conform to stereotypical masculine and feminine gender roles can also be bullied. The findings from the univariate analyses indicated that LGBTQ+ adolescents experienced higher rates of victimization—both homophobic and non-homophobic—compared to their straight peers. The regressions showed that homophobic bullying was linked to male heterosexuality, while homophobic victimization was associated with low levels of prejudice, particularly against LGBQ youth (Camodeca et al., 2018).

Many Africans, belonging to various groups, are vehemently against and critical of same-sex partnerships. The continent has seen a surge in the criminalization of same-sex partnerships in the twenty-first century. *Apocalyptic Homophobia: Freedom of Religious Expression, Hate Speech, and the Pentecostal Discourse on Same-Sex Relations in Africa* (Ukah, 2021).

According to (Pocan, J. 2022), an explanatory sequential mixed-method design was employed in this study to investigate the discrimination encountered by LGBTQA intercollegiate athletes from private and public higher education institutions in the Philippines. The results demonstrate that participants frequently encountered verbal and/or sexist abuse at different times and places, that individuals who inflicted such abuse were typically either supporters or members of the crowd, and that the most common response to assault was to avoid the abuse.

In the present study, we focus on the relationship between democratic deficits and homophobic divergence within 21st-century European societies (Rodríguez and Murtagh, 2022). The researchers aim to investigate how shortcomings in democratic processes or values within European nations might be associated with variations in attitudes and discriminatory practices related to sexual orientation. The focus on the 21st century suggests an interest in understanding these dynamics in the context of modern societal, political, and cultural developments. "Homophobic divergence" refers to variations or differences in attitudes, beliefs, and discriminatory practices related to sexual orientation, specifically those directed against individuals who identify as LGBTQ+ (lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, or any combination of these).

According to Phan et al. (2020), the existence or lack of this perception significantly impacts an individual's self-esteem and mental health within the complicated context of

the LGBT community's lived experiences. Continuous exposure to discriminatory attitudes can lead individuals to internalize negative experiences.

Research Questions

This study confirms how different generations perceive modern homophobia. It specifically sought responses to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Civil Status;
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment; and
 - 1.5 Religion?
2. What is the n of the respondents on modern homophobia when grouped according to:
 - 2.1 Lesbian; and
 - 2.2 Gay?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on modern homophobia?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their perception of modern homophobia?
5. What gender development program can be proposed to promote gender sensitivity?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This research was conducted in Marikina City, Philippines, under the supervision of the research professor and adviser. Marikina, formally known as the metropolis of Marikina, was a first-class, highly urbanized city located in the Philippines' National Capital Region. As per the 2020 census, the population of the area was 456,159. Marikina was famously known as the "Shoe Capital of the Philippines" due to its prominent shoe industry. This city was the country's largest shoe manufacturer, responsible for producing approximately 70% of the shoes made in the Philippines. The Philippine International Footwear Center and the Shoe Museum were both situated in the city. Additionally, the researchers had chosen Generation X, Y, and Z of Marikina City, Philippines, as the research site to delve deeper into the effects of modern homophobia observed in Generation X, Y, and Z.

Research Design

A type of quantitative research design, called descriptive correlational research design, used observational methods or surveys to collect data in order to analyze the relationships between variables and answer the question, "How were things related?"

While observation involved watching video records or utilizing the experience sampling approach to acquire real-time data on participants' experiences, surveys were an effective way to learn about people's experiences, views, and attitudes. There was no manipulation of the main area of interest in this design. One of the main benefits of descriptive correlational research design was its ability to provide insight into actual phenomena. Researchers could gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between various elements by examining the correlations between variables in their natural environments. For example, a study might have explored the connection between a community's residents' income and their level of education. It was crucial to remember that causality could not be established using descriptive correlational research designs (Fowler, 2013).

Research Participants

The research study titled "Perception on Modern Homophobia of Diverse Generations" sought to investigate the perception of a diverse generation toward modern homophobia within the age range referred to as the diverse generation. The diverse generation was referred to as Generation X, Y, and Z. The age range of Generation X was from 44 years old to 59 years old, the age range of Generation Y, also called Millennials, was from 28 years old to 43 years old, and lastly, Generation Z was from 12 years old to 27 years old. There were 120 participants in this study, all living in Marikina City. The researcher used purposive sampling as a technique to select the participants. By choosing individuals based on particular characteristics, the research aimed to explore the perceptions of Generation X, Y, and Z on homosexuality.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaires and approval later served as the study's instruments. The purpose of the permission letter is to obtain authorization for carrying out the research and to collect data from the respondents, who are the citizens of Marikina City. In order to achieve the study's goal of understanding Perception on Modern Homophobia of Diverse Generation, a questionnaire is employed to collect data from the sample. In order to achieve the study's goal of understanding the perception of modern homophobia of Generation X, Y, and Z, a questionnaire is employed to collect data from the sample. For the survey questionnaire to be completed, 120 responses are required.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers adopted an online survey questionnaire and permission letter to conduct the study. The letter was submitted to the World Citi Colleges – Quezon City for approval. The survey questionnaire included questions related to attitudes towards LGBTQ+ individuals and demographic information. The questionnaire was validated by consulting with professors in the field of research to help ensure that the questions were reliable and valid. It was administered online using a platform such as Google Forms. The survey was distributed through email invitations or social media. Participants were informed about the purpose of the survey, the voluntary nature of participation, and any incentives or rewards for completing the survey. The target population was defined as individuals from

Generation X, Y, and Z who resided in a specific geographic area or were members of a specific organization or community. The sample size was large enough to provide sufficient statistical power for the analysis, with at least 120 participants. The researchers used purposive sampling to select a sample of 120 participants from the target population. This method helped ensure that the sample was representative of the population. The researchers collected the responses from the participants and analyzed the data using appropriate statistical methods. The results were used to test the research hypotheses and draw conclusions about the relationships between moral disengagement, religiosity, and modern homophobia among Generation X, Y, and Z individuals.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the perception of modern homophobia among individuals from different generations residing in Marikina City. It explored how different generations in Marikina City understood modern homophobia and examined the factors influencing their perspectives. The study compared the opinions of respondents from Generation X, Generation Y, and Generation Z. However, the study's limitations included its age and geographic focus, cultural background, and time constraints.

Data Analysis

One-way ANOVA

One-way ANOVA is a statistical test used to compare the average values of three or more groups to see if they are different from each other. It helps determine if any differences in the group averages are likely due to the actual effect or just random chance. However, it doesn't tell you which specific groups are different, only that at least one group is not the same as the others.

Pearson R

Pearson's R is a statistic that measures how strongly two variables are related and whether they move together in a positive or negative way. The value of Pearson's r ranges from -1 to 1. A value near 1 means a strong positive relationship (as one variable goes up, so does the other), while a value near -1 means a strong negative relationship (as one goes up, the other goes down). A value around 0 means there's no clear relationship between the two variables.

Spearman Rho

Spearman's rho is a statistic that measures how strongly two ranked variables are related. It shows whether the rankings of the two variables move together in the same direction (positive correlation) or in opposite directions (negative correlation). The value ranges from -1 to 1, with values close to 1 or -1 indicating a strong relationship, and values near 0 indicating little to no relationship.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table1

Respondents profile in terms of Age

Socio-Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Age	11 to 26 years old	40	33.3
	27 to 43 years old	40	33.3
	44 to 59 years old	40	33.3

The demographic profile of the N=120 respondents are presented in the table 1. With regards to age, there is an equal representation among the respondents, 40 individuals are within the age range of 11-26 (33.33%) years old similarly, 40 individuals are within the age range of 27-43 (33.33%) years old and the rest are within the age range of 44-59 (33.33%).

Table2

Respondent's profile in terms of Gender

Socio-Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Gender	Male	50	40.7
	Female	69	57.5
	Prefer not to say	1	.8

On the other hand, the sex composition of the participants was dominantly female, represented by 69 individuals (57.5%) and 50 individuals were identified as male (41.57%). The remaining 0.8% was recorded from a respondent who prefers not to report their sex.

Table3

Respondent's profile in terms of Civil Status

Socio-Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Civil Status	Single	78	65.0
	Married	27	22.5
	Widow/Widower	6	5.0
	Separated	9	7.5

Civil status was also recorded and dominantly, respondents are single represented by 78 individuals (65%). The rest of the respondents are married (22.5%), widow/widower (5%) and separated (7.5%).

Table4

Respondent's profile in terms of Religion

Socio-Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Religion	Roman Catholic	83	69.2
	Christian	23	19.2

Iglesia ni Cristo	11	9.2
Southern Baptist	2	1.7
Dating Daan	1	.8

With the varying religion groups, here are the following religion representation identified: 83 individuals are Roman Catholics (69.2%), 23 individuals are Christian (19.2%), 11 individuals are Iglesia ni Cristo (9.2%), 2 individuals are Southern Baptist (1.7%) and 1 individual is Dating daan (0.85).

Table 5

Respondent's profile in terms of Educational Attainment

Socio-Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Educational Attainment	College Graduate	35	29.2
	College Level	40	33.3
	High School Graduate	20	16.7
	High School Level	15	12.5
	Elementary Graduate	5	4.2
	Elementary Level	4	3.3
	No Formal Schooling	1	.8

The highest educational attainment was also demonstrated in table 5, it suggests that most of the respondents are on college level represented by 40 individuals (33.33%) followed by 35 college graduates (29.2%), 20 high school graduates (16.7%), 15 high school students (12.5%), 5 elementary graduates (4.2%), 4 elementary students (3.3%) and 1 who reported no formal schooling (0.85). In terms of the respondent's Modern Homophobia (MHS-L), results show an overall weighted mean of 3.48. Out of 24 items on the scale, respondents' views were mostly neutral or somewhat supportive of lesbian rights and acceptance. The highest mean was for the statement that teachers should try to reduce their student's prejudice toward lesbians (M=4.11) indicating a somewhat positive attitude towards proactive measures against prejudice. Conversely, the lowest mean was for the statement that female homosexuality is a psychological disease (M=2.28), reflecting a general disagreement with this negative and outdated belief. Overall, the respondents displayed a neutral stance on modern homophobia (M=3.48). This suggests that while there is some level of acceptance, there are still areas where attitudes could be more progressive. The following groupings of data are identified by the legend: 1:00-1:49 Not at all; 1:50-2:49 Not Very Much; 2:50-3:49 Neutral; 3:50-4:49 Somewhat; 4:50-5:00 Very Much. It facilitates research by determining a question's verbal interpretation.

Table 6

Respondent's perception on Modern Homophobia (MHS-L)

Modern Homophobia Questions (MHS-L)	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Employers should provide health care benefits to the partners of their lesbian employee.	4.04	Somewhat
Teachers should try to reduce their student's prejudice toward lesbians.	4.11	Somewhat

Lesbians who adopt children do not need to be monitored more closely than heterosexual parents.	3.84	Somewhat
Lesbians should be allowed to be leaders in religious organizations.	3.84	Somewhat
Lesbians are as capable as heterosexuals of forming long-term romantic relationships.	4.07	Somewhat
School curricula should include positive discussion of lesbian topics.	4.03	Somewhat
Marriages between two lesbians should be legal.	3.60	Somewhat
Lesbians should not be allowed to join the military.	2.60	Neutral
I would not vote for a political candidate who was openly lesbian.	2.59	Neutral
Lesbians are incapable of being good parents.	2.74	Neutral
I am tired of hearing about lesbians' problems.	2.71	Neutral
I wouldn't mind going to a party that includes lesbians.	3.84	Somewhat
I wouldn't mind working with a lesbian.	3.94	Somewhat
I am comfortable with the thought of two women being romantically involved.	3.99	Somewhat
It's alright with me if I see two women holding hands.	4.07	Somewhat
If my best female friend was dating a woman, it would not upset me.	4.09	Somewhat
Movies that approve of female homosexuality bother me.	2.60	Neutral
I welcome new friends who are lesbian.	4.02	Somewhat
I don't mind companies using openly lesbian celebrities to advertise their products.	4	Somewhat
I would be sure to invite the same-sex partner of my lesbian friend to my party.	3.95	Somewhat
I don't think it would negatively affect our relationship if I learned that one of my close relatives was lesbian.	3.89	Somewhat
Physicians and psychologists should strive to find a cure for female homosexuality.	2.52	Neutral
Lesbians should undergo therapy to change their sexual orientation.	2.32	Not Very
Female homosexuality is a Psychological Disease.	2.28	Not Very
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Neutral

Legend:

1:00-1:49 Not at all 1:50-2:49 Not very much 2:50-3:49 Neutral
3:50-4:49 Somewhat 4:50-5:00 Very Much

Table 7

Respondent's perception in Modern Homophobia (MHS-G)

Modern Homophobia Questions (MHS-G)	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I wouldn't mind going to a party that included gay men.	4.10	Somewhat
I would not mind working with a gay man.	4.25	Somewhat
I welcome new friends who are gay.	4.24	Somewhat
I would be sure to invite the same-sex partner of my gay male friend to my party.	4.08	Somewhat
I won't associate with a gay man for fear of catching AIDS.	2.85	Neutral
I don't think it would negatively affect our relationships if I learned that one of my close relatives was gay.	3.91	Somewhat
I am comfortable with the thought of two men being romantically involved.	4.01	Somewhat
I would remove my child from class if I found out the teacher was gay.	2.38	Not Very
It's alright with me if I see two men holding hands.	3.95	Somewhat

Male homosexuality is a psychological disease.	2.39	Not Very
Physicians and psychologists should strive to find cure for male homosexuality.	2.48	Not Very
Gay men should undergo therapy to change their sexual orientation.	2.32	Not Very
Gay men could be heterosexual if they really wanted to be.	3.22	Neutral
I don't mind companies using openly gay male celebrities to advertise their product.	3.93	Somewhat
I would not vote for a political candidate who was openly gay.	2.42	Not Very
Hospitals shouldn't hire gay male doctors.	2.38	Not Very
Gay men shouldn't be allowed to join the military.	2.47	Not Very
Movies that approve of male homosexuality bother me.	2.61	Neutral
Gay men should not be allowed to be leaders in religious organizations.	2.68	Neutral
Marriages between two gay men should be legal.	3.47	Neutral
I am tired of hearing about gay men's problems.	2.61	Neutral
Gay men want too many rights.	3.06	Neutral
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	Neutral

Legend:

1:00-1:49 Not at all 1:50-2:49 Not Very Much 2:50-3:49 Neutral
3:50-4:49 Somewhat 4:50-5:00 Very Much

In terms of the respondent's Modern Homophobia (MHS-G), results show an overall weighted mean of 3.17. Out of 22 items on the scale, respondents' views were mostly neutral regarding gay rights and acceptance. The highest mean was for the statement "I would not mind working with a gay man" (M=4.25), indicating a somewhat positive attitude towards working relationships with gay men. Conversely, the lowest mean was for the statement "Gay men should undergo therapy to change their sexual orientation" (M=2.32), reflecting a general disagreement with this negative and outdated belief. Overall, the respondents displayed a neutral stance on modern homophobia (M=3.17). This suggests that while there is some level of acceptance, there are still areas where attitudes could be more progressive. The following groupings of data are identified by the legend: 1:00-1:49 Not at all; 1:50-2:49 Not Very Much; 2:50-3:49 Neutral; 3:50-4:49 Somewhat; 4:50-5:00 Very Much. It facilitates research by determining a question's verbal interpretation.

Table8

Perception levels of the respondents

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Modern Homophobia (MH)	120	2.00	5.00	3.3365	.51971

Depicted in the table above are the perception levels of the respondents in terms of Modern Homophobia (MH), Modern Homophobia got a mean value of 3.34 with a minimum value of 2.00 and maximum value of 5.00 considering 5-Point Likert type of test.

Standard deviation which explains how the scores are dispersed in a distribution was accounted to. 52 hence, scores fell just around the mean with minimal variation observed across data points. In essence, modern homophobia (M=3.34; SD=.52).

Table 9
Significant Relationship of Modern Homophobia using Demographic Profile of Respondents

Indicators	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Age	1.500	.227	Accepted	There is no significant relationship
Sex	1.656	.195	Accepted	There is no significant relationship
Civil Status	1.072	.364	Accepted	There is no significant relationship
Educational Attainment	.740	.638	Accepted	There is no significant relationship
Religion	1.807	.132	Accepted	There is no significant relationship

With an alpha value of 0.05 here are the following findings as demonstrated in table 9: Null hypothesis failed to be rejected the age set of indicators hence, there is no significant relationship on the level of perception on Modern Homophobia when respondents are grouped according to age [F(2,117) = 1.500, p < .227].

Null hypothesis was failed to be rejected the sex set of indicators hence, there is no significant relationship on the level of perception on Modern Homophobia (M=3.34; SD=.52) when respondents are grouped to sex [F(2,117) = 1.656, p < .195] Null hypothesis failed to be rejected the civil status set of indicators hence, there is no significant relationship on the level of perception on MH when respondents are grouped according to civil status [F(3,116) = 1.072, p < .364]. Null hypothesis failed to be rejected the educational attainment set of indicators hence, there is no significant relationship on the level of perception on Modern Homophobia when respondents are grouped according to educational attainment [F(4,115) = .740,p<.638]. Lastly, Null hypothesis failed to be rejected the religion in the set of indicators hence, there is no significant relationship on the level of perception on Modern Homophobia when respondents are grouped according to religion [F(4,115) = 1.807, p < .132).

DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The purpose of this study was to assess the level of modern homophobia among Generations X, Y, and Z. The researchers concluded that there was equal representation among the respondents, with 40 people falling into the 11–26 age range, 40 respondents in the 27–43 age range, and the remaining respondents in the 44–59 age range. In terms of the respondents' gender makeup, 50 (42.57%) participants identified as male, while 69 (57.5%) identified as female. The remaining 0.8% of respondents chose to

remain anonymous. Regarding marital status, 65% of respondents were single, while 22.5% were married, 5% were widows or widowers, and 7.5% were separated. Religious affiliation included 83 Roman Catholics (69.2%), 23 Christians (19.2%), 11 Iglesia ni Cristo members (9.2%), 2 Southern Baptists (1.7%), and 1 member of the Dating Daan group (0.85%). The highest level of education attained by the respondents was college (33.33%), followed by high school (16.7%), elementary school (4.2%), and no formal education (3.3%).

Respondents' perception on Modern Homophobia (MHS-L)

The results of the respondents' assessments on contemporary lesbian homophobia are shown in Table 8. The data reveals that the respondents' Modern Homophobia Scale (MHS-L) had an overall weighted mean of 3.48. Across the 24 questions on the scale, the majority of respondents' views were either neutral or slightly in favor of lesbian acceptance and rights. The statement "teachers should try to reduce their students' prejudice toward lesbians" had the highest mean ($M = 4.11$), indicating some support for taking strong action against prejudice. Conversely, the statement that female homosexuality is a psychological disorder had the lowest mean ($M = 2.28$), suggesting widespread opposition to this outdated and negative viewpoint. Overall, the respondents' views on modern homophobia were generally neutral ($M = 3.48$). This indicates that, while some acceptance exists, attitudes toward homophobia should still become more progressive and impartial.

Respondents' perception on Modern Homophobia (MHS-G)

Table 9 presents the findings from the respondents' perceptions of modern homophobia toward gay individuals. The study on respondents' Modern Homophobia Scale (MHS-G) found an overall weighted mean of 3.17, indicating generally neutral attitudes toward gay rights and acceptance. The statement "I would not mind working with a gay man" had the highest mean ($M = 4.25$), showing a positive attitude toward sexual orientation. On the other hand, the statement "Gay people should not be allowed to adopt children" had the lowest mean ($M = 2.32$), demonstrating widespread disagreement with this negative belief. Overall, respondents took a neutral view of modern homophobia, indicating some acceptance but also highlighting areas where more progressive attitudes are needed. Recent studies indicate a trend toward greater acceptance of LGBTQ+ individuals, particularly in Western countries, though significant areas still require progress. This suggests that while some level of acceptance exists, there are still areas where attitudes could become more progressive. Although blatant forms of homophobia have decreased, modern homophobia manifests more subtly through microaggressions and institutional biases (Dewaele et al., 2021).

Perception levels of the Respondents

The table 10 shows respondents' perceptions of Modern Homophobia (MH). Modern Homophobia had a mean of 3.34, scores ranging from 2.00 to 5.00, and a standard deviation of 0.52, indicating the least fluctuation of the three categories. With 120

respondents, modern homophobia scored ($M=3.34$; $SD=0.52$). Overall, the scores for all three measures were close to the averages, indicating that the individuals responded consistently.

Significant Relationship of Modern homophobia using demographic profile of respondents

The study in Table 3, with an alpha value of 0.05, reveals no significant connections between the level of perception of Modern Homophobia and numerous demographic variables. The null hypothesis was not rejected for age [$F(2, 117) = 1.500, p = 0.227$], sex [$F(2, 177) = 1.656, p = 0.195$], civil status [$F(3, 116) = 1.072, p = 0.364$], educational attainment [$F(4, 115) = 0.740, p = 0.638$], and religion [$F(4, 115) = 1.807, p = 0.132$]. These findings show that the respondents' perceptions of Modern Homophobia ($M=3.34, SD=0.52$) are not significantly influenced by age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, or religion. As a result, demographic characteristics have no influence on respondents' perceptions of current homophobia. In a study by Martinez and Johnson (2018), the researchers explored the relationship between moral disengagement and hate crimes targeting the LGBTQ+ community. The findings revealed that individuals who scored higher on measures of moral disengagement were more likely to engage in hate crimes against sexual minorities, highlighting the role of moral disengagement in perpetuating homophobic violence.

Conclusions

The 120 respondents in the study were surveyed in Marikina City. The distribution of respondents across these generational groups—46.6% from Generation X, 24.5% from Generation Y, and 27.6% from Generation Z—provides a comprehensive analysis of how different generations interpret modern homophobia. There was an equal representation of men and women among the participants, with 50 identifying as men and 69 as women. Among the respondents, 7.5% were separated, 5% were widows or widowers, and the remaining 22.5% were married. College graduates had the highest level of education, followed by individuals with only an elementary education, a high school diploma, and those with no formal education. Among the various religious communities represented in the survey, there were 23 Christians, 11 members of the Iglesia Ni Cristo, 2 Southern Baptists, 83 Roman Catholics, and 1 member of the Dating Daan.

The results show that the respondents' Modern Homophobia Scale (MHS-L) had an overall weighted mean of 3.48. Across the 24 questions on the scale, the majority of respondents' views were either neutral or slightly in favor of lesbian acceptance and rights. The study on respondents' Modern Homophobia Scale (MHS-G) revealed an overall weighted mean of 3.17, indicating generally neutral sentiments toward gay rights and acceptance. It is crucial that researchers, educators, and legislators continue their efforts to promote awareness and foster conversation on LGBTQ+ rights issues by engaging with people from different backgrounds and confronting prejudices. This study's conclusions have several implications for practice, research, and the educational field. Such studies can offer deeper insights into the specific needs and challenges faced by

the community, guiding the development of targeted solutions. Moreover, understanding modern homophobia enables us to become stronger allies of the LGBTQ+ community. By being knowledgeable about and aware of the challenges they face, researchers and educators can provide support, understanding, and solidarity in their pursuit of equality and recognition.

Recommendations

This study revealed the perceptions of modern homophobia across diverse generations. Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

To promote acceptance of all sexual orientations, educational workshops and seminars should be organized. These events will focus on inclusivity and understanding. Additionally, engaging the community—including young people, families, schools, and local groups—will help support and spread acceptance. Campaigns can involve everyone in fostering understanding and acceptance of different sexual orientations. This approach aims to create a more welcoming and inclusive society.

It is important to note that people may not always be truthful in surveys, particularly when discussing sensitive topics like attitudes toward homosexuality. Different age groups and cultures may hold varying opinions on these issues. Recognizing this diversity helps us understand people better. To address these challenges, educational programs can be developed to promote empathy and highlight the negative effects of discrimination. These programs can encourage people to better understand others and to view issues from different perspectives.

To further promote acceptance of all sexual orientations, community leaders should be invited to discuss the connection between gender equality and inclusivity. Additionally, educating the community about modern homophobia will enhance understanding and reduce discrimination.

Creating safe spaces for open discussions about attitudes toward homosexuality is crucial for promoting understanding and inclusivity in communities. These spaces provide individuals with the opportunity to share their thoughts without fear of judgment or discrimination.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

While there were several ethical considerations that needed to be made, they all primarily dealt with the same fundamental issues. Examples included participant well-being, confidentiality, respect for others, and data security. Throughout the study process, it was the researcher's responsibility to ensure that all ethical guidelines were followed.

Participants were informed by the researchers that declining to participate would not have any unfavorable effects. They were giving their time to help with the research, and thus

the researchers were expected to respect their opinions without trying to influence them. The scenario the researchers were referring to was one in which every potential participant received and fully understood all of the information needed to decide whether or not to join. Anonymity could only be guaranteed if researchers refrained from gathering any personally identifying information, including names, phone numbers, email addresses, IP addresses, physical characteristics, pictures, and videos. Participants were assured by the researchers that their information would be kept private.

The researchers were always expected to retain secrecy, even if they were unable to gather data in an anonymous manner. Researchers had to be cautious to fully disclose to participants all possible risks of harm before beginning a study in order to acquire informed consent. If there was a chance of danger, researchers were ready to offer participants assistance, therapy, or medical care. There were times when ethical questions were raised by the way researchers published the results of their research. Good science communication was credible, dependable, and trustworthy. It was also excellent when the findings were as clear-cut as possible. The act of submitting someone else's work as your own was known as plagiarism. Even when it was done unintentionally, stealing occurred when someone copied another person's work without giving due credit. In research communication, it was an ethical dilemma because researchers could gain by generating.

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